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THE ACTION OF HYDROXYANTHRACENIC DERIVATIVES IN SIMPLE AND PHYTO-COMPLEX FORM OF ALOE ON THE CELL NUCLEUS

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Abstract:

This study aims to establish the action on the cellular activity of HAD Hydroxyanthracenic Derivatives as a mixture of polar molecules (Aloin, Aloe Emodin) and as a total plant complex towards haploid cells and in particular the effect that these molecules can have on the nucleus of the eukaryotic cell

Material: Organisms Used Haploid Cells Organism Model Yeast *Saccharomyces Cerevisiae*, Aloe ferox L.

Premise:

The choice of using *Saccharomyces Cerevisiae* cells lies in the fact that this microorganism has many similarities with mammalian cells.

For this it is an excellent model organism, to shed light on different human cellular mechanisms.

Method:

The cells were exposed to the test substances (A = Aloin + Aloe Emodin + Ethyl Acetate (as exogenous metabolic activator) B = Ethyl Acetate + Phytocomplex)

Results

The results of the cellular treatment report that in Yeast cultures marked with A containing Aloin, Aloe Emodin there was a strong nuclear activity while in B cells containing the Phytocomplex the activity was almost zero, this activity was compared with cultures of control subjected to the same treatment that detected a nuclear activity within the norm.

CHANGE AND STATE OF PROGRESS NUCLEUS IN SAMPLE A

A: The Nucleus of the Cell in contact with the A mixture appears to have a strong Nuclear activity

SAMPLE CORE STATUS B:

B: The Nucleus of the Cell in contact with the Phytocomplex B appears with low Nuclear activity

Conclusion:

These studies show how the single polar molecules or mixtures of them of Hydroxyanthracen HAD can have an activating effect on the cell nucleus, this must be kept under control for any cancerous degeneration, but it shows that the same molecules taken with all the phytocomplex of the plant they are completely irrelevant as regards any effects on the nucleus and therefore the possible cell degeneration into neoplastic forms.

REFERENCES:

Warburg effect and translocation-induced genomic instability: two yeast models for cancer cells

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